

Peer Review in EFL Writing: Teacher Attitudes

Jeremy White
Ritsumeikan University
Kyoto, Japan

Brett Morgan
Ritsumeikan University
Kyoto, Japan

Bjorn Fuisting
Ritsumeikan University
Kyoto, Japan

Peer review in writing entails the act of students providing feedback on their peers' writing, and is widely used in second language learning (L2) classrooms that employ a process-oriented approach to writing. In this approach, writing is viewed as a recursive process involving planning, writing, and reviewing, and thus usually involves production of multiple drafts (Hayes & Flower, 1980). The process approach puts less emphasis on summative feedback, which focuses on writing as a product, instead employing formative feedback in the reviewing stage with the intent of developing students' writing abilities. This has led L2 researchers to inquire how different sources of feedback can be effectively provided. Some English as a Foreign Language (EFL) research (Nelson & Carson, 1998; Zhang, 1995) has found that students strongly preferred teacher to peer feedback. However, EFL studies in east Asian contexts (Jacobs, Curtis, Braine, & Huang, 1998; Tsui & Ng, 2000) have demonstrated that most students wanted peer feedback when teacher feedback was additionally assured, highlighting the view that incorporating teachers and peers as complementary sources of feedback in addition to self-review might be the best approach for process writing classrooms. Most research has focused on this field from a student perspective. With peer review (also referred

to as peer editing in this article) becoming a staple of many EFL writing programs, the researchers feel there is a need for examination of the attitudes of teachers in relation to conducting peer review. Do EFL teachers think peer review is a practical, worthwhile classroom activity? Do they view it as an effective learning tool? What insights can teachers provide from their experiences with peer review? This mixed method study investigates the attitudes towards peer review of 41 EFL instructors in the Japanese university context.

Theoretical Basis

With the potential offered by its interactive nature, peer review finds strong theoretical support in two learning theories. Vygotsky's (1978, 1986) social-constructivist approach asserts that social interaction is crucial for cognitive language development. Particularly relevant is Vygotsky's notion of a zone of proximal development, defined as the distance between an individual's actual and potential levels of development, which can be partly bridged with the assistance of one's peers (1978, p. 86). Similarly, collaborative learning theory (Bruffee, 1984; Hirvela, 1999) calls for learners to complete challenging tasks through interaction with peers and the pooling of learners' differing abilities.

Benefits & Difficulties with Peer Review

A variety of benefits have been claimed from the use of peer review in L2 writing. Chaudron (1984) found that peer review reduced writer apprehension and increased learner autonomy in ESL writers. Min (2005) demonstrated that it improved attitudes towards writing and promoted EFL learners' use of metacognitive strategies. Peer review has also been found to help L2 students develop self-awareness as writers and enhance audience awareness (Tsui & Ng, 2000), aid L2 acquisition (Lockhart & Ng, 1995), and result in better final compositions (Paulus, 1999). Clearly, the use of peer review in EFL classrooms has the potential to offer affective, cognitive, and linguistic benefits for learners.

Some research has drawn attention to the difficulties of using peer review in L2 classrooms. Nelson and Murphy (1992) argued that the complexity of the peer review process limits its usefulness in L2 environments. Leki (1990) asserted that L2 learners are usually incapable of providing concrete, useful feedback. Cultural characteristics have also been implicated in difficulties with peer review, with some researchers suggesting that learners from Asian cultures with a collectivist orientation may find it difficult to be openly critical of their peers' writing (Nelson & Carson, 1998).

Implementation of Peer Review

A key area of interest for researchers has been in how to effectively implement peer review in L2 classrooms. Some researchers (Min, 2005; Paulus, 1999) have argued that forming face-to-face pairs is preferable to small groups when implementing peer review as students preferred pairs and had more communicative opportunities. Some studies have tried to ascertain whether feedback given anonymously resulted in more effective peer feedback (Hosack, 2003; Silver & Coomber, 2011), with results suggesting some value in anonymous feedback for classes consisting predominantly of female students. Chang (2012) demonstrated the effectiveness of both synchronous and asynchronous computer-mediated modes of peer review, which could offer engaging future avenues to explore. Other research has focused on training students to give feedback on their peers' writing. Berg (1999)

and Min (2005) found that extensive training programs resulted in more meaningful revisions and higher quality writing, although the amount of time invested in training students in these studies is not feasible in many educational contexts. The literature demonstrates that different modes of peer review and training should be strongly considered when designing a peer review process.

Attitudes Towards Peer Review

Many studies in various EFL contexts have reported favorable student attitudes towards peer feedback (Jacobs et al., 1998; Morra & Romano, 2008; Moussaoui, 2012; Tsui & Ng, 2000). Studies conducted in Japanese university contexts have also found that students generally find value in peer review writing activities (Coomber & Silver, 2010; Hirose, 2008; Taferner, 2008, 2009; Wakabayashi, 2008). The researchers' (Morgan, Fuisting, & White, 2014) survey of 125 students at the same university as the current study found generally positive attitudes towards peer review in writing. They found that students were not overly concerned about criticizing each other and that peer review somewhat increased their enjoyment of writing. They further discovered that students greatly doubted their own peer review abilities and were reluctant to show their writing, but that they trusted their classmates' abilities and wanted to read their peers' work.

Jeremy White is an associate professor at Ritsumeikan University, Japan. He is currently studying for an EdD in CALL and video game use in the classroom at Griffith University.

Most EFL studies concerned with attitudes towards peer review have focused on the views of learners. An examination of attitudes towards teacher feedback in an Indonesian university (Zacharias, 2007) included surveys and interviews with instructors, finding that many teachers placed little faith in peer review because of students' collectivist orientations. A study in Argentina (Morra & Romano, 2008) included interviews with two instructors, finding they were positive about the peer review process and observed affective benefits in their students. However, little significant research focusing on EFL teachers' attitudes towards peer review has been conducted in Asia. This is the primary impetus for the current study.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this mixed method study is to examine teachers' attitudes towards peer review in EFL writing activities. Specifically, this study will focus on teachers' attitudes in relation to relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, results demonstrability, and peer review experience. It is hoped that examination of teachers' perceptions of peer review and their classroom experiences with it can provide valuable insights into how the peer review process can be effectively implemented in EFL writing classes both in Japan and within a broader context.

Research Questions

The research questions were: (a) What are teachers' attitudes towards peer review in EFL writing in relation to relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, and demonstrability? And (b) What forms of peer review do instructors use in their classes, what benefits do they perceive from it, and how does the experience of conducting peer review differ amongst Japanese and foreign instructors?

Methodology

The instrument used for data collection was a paper-based survey consisting of original questions drafted by the researchers with input from colleagues. Surveys were sent to 101 instructors, both Japanese and foreign, and a total of 41 were returned. The survey was trialed with instructors from another university, with subsequent feedback concerning clarity and relevance informing changes to the survey. The survey contained quantitative and qualitative questions. The framework for the quantitative section of the survey was based on a technology innovation research model developed by Rogers (1983) and Moore and Benbasat (1991). This framework, while not specifically designed for pedagogical analysis, most closely reflected the objectives of the current study. The questions in the quantitative part of the survey were posed as statements and teachers were asked to circle the number best corresponding with their level of agreement with the statement on a 6-point Likert scale, with an optional comment section for each question. The survey started with demographic questions, followed by the first subsection concerning the relative advantage of peer review. Relative advantage for this survey is defined as the degree to which conducting peer review is perceived

to be better than not doing peer review. The second subsection explored the compatibility of peer review with the instructor's teaching style. Compatibility here is defined as the degree to which peer review is perceived as being consistent with the values, needs, and past experiences of teachers. The third section was related to the complexity of peer review. Complexity is defined as the degree to which the instructor believes peer review is difficult to use. The fourth section explored the demonstrability of peer review. Demonstrability is defined as the visible impact that peer review has on students' writing abilities. The qualitative section of this survey contained five open-ended questions where participants were asked to give comments about their experiences using peer review. The survey can be found in the Appendix. Quantitative data were analyzed using a combination of Microsoft Excel and SPSS statistical software, while the comments received were thematically coded to allow for a qualitative analysis.

Demographic Characteristics

Thirty-three (33) of the participants were full time instructors (80.5%) while 8 were part time instructors (19.5%). Fifteen (15) participants were Japanese (36.6%) while 26 were foreign (63.4%). The majority of the respondents were from the Economic and Business Administration departments.

Relative Advantage

The second section of the survey was used to collect data regarding perceptions of relative advantage. Table 1 is a summary of responses.

Table 1

Relative Advantage

n	Mean	Mode	Median	Low-High	Range	SD
1. Using peer editing reduces my time spent on correcting writing						
41	3.63	4	4	1-6	5	1
2. Peer editing is a good use of class time						
41	4.44	4	4	2-6	4	0.5

Note: 1-strongly disagree, 2-disagree, 3-somewhat disagree, 4-somewhat agree, 5-agree, 6-strongly agree

Compatibility

The third section collected data related to compatibility. Table 2 is a summary of responses.

Table 2

Compatibility

n	Mean	Mode	Median	Low-High	Range	SD
1. Peer editing is compatible with my teaching style.						
41	4.80	5.00	5.00	1-6	3	1.00
2. Peer editing is a good way to review writing.						
41	4.78	5.00	5.00	2-6	3	0.50

Complexity

The fourth section collected data in relation to complexity. Table 3 is a summary of responses.

Table 3

Complexity

n	Mean	Mode	Median	Low-High	Range	SD
1. Peer editing is easy to implement.						
41	3.93	5.00	4.00	3-6	4	1.50
2. Students need to be trained before they can implement peer editing.						
41	5.27	6.00	6.00	3-6	4	1.00

Demonstrability

The fifth section collected data related to the demonstrability of peer editing. Table 4 is a summary of responses.

Table 4

Demonstrability

n	Mean	Mode	Median	Low-High	Range	SD
1. Peer editing increases the quality of students' final papers.						
41	4.39	4.00	5.00	2-6	5	1.00
2. Peer editing helps students understand academic writing better.						
41	4.71	5.00	5.00	2-6	4	1.00

Peer Review Experience

The last section of the survey collected data regarding experience with various forms of peer review. Table 5 shows the numerical data for the yes/no response sections, further contrasted in relation to differences between Japanese and foreign instructors. The first number in each column is the raw score out of 41 teachers. The second is the percentage of the 41 teachers, and the third score is the percentage divided by nationality. Qualitative results from the corresponding open-ended questions are presented in the discussion subsection.

Table 5

Peer Review Experience

n	Japanese		Foreign		No answer	
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Japanese	Foreign
1. Do you use peer editing in your English classes?						
41	6 (14.6%) (40.0%)	23 (56.1%) (88.5%)	7 (17.1%) (46.7%)	3 (7.3%) (11.5%)	2 (4.9%) (13.3%)	0 (0.0%) (0.0%)
2. Do you feel there are benefits of using peer editing in the classroom?						
41	7 (17.1%) (46.7%)	24 (58.5%) (92.4%)	0 (0.0%) (0.0%)	1 (2.4%) (3.8%)	8 (19.5%) (53.3%)	1 (2.4%) (3.8%)
3. Do you use any other form of peer review?						
41	5 (12.2%) (33.3%)	14 (34.1%) (53.8%)	2 (4.9%) (13.3%)	10 (24.4%) (38.5%)	8 (19.5%) (53.3%)	2 (4.9%) (13.3%)
4. Do you use any form of peer evaluation?						
41	6 (14.6%) (40.0%)	17 (41.5%) (65.4%)	3 (7.3%) (6.7%)	7 (17.1%) (65.4%)	6 (14.6%) (40.0%)	2 (4.9%) (7.7%)

Discussion

Relative Advantage

The first statement, "using peer editing reduces my time spent on correcting writing," had a median and mode of 4.00, suggesting that teachers slightly agree, but lack confidence in this statement. A median of 3.63 provides further evidence to the neutral result. The second statement, "peer editing is a good use of class time," also had a median and mode of 4.00. However, the mean of 4.44 suggests that in comparison to the previous statement there is a slightly more positive view in relation to peer editing being a worthwhile activity. Analyzing both statements illustrates instructors have a slightly positive attitude to the relative advantage of using peer editing in their classes, but do not believe their time spent correcting errors will be reduced significantly. Comments from teachers provide further evidence to this, with one teacher stating that while peer editing may produce better writing, the time spent grading remains unchanged.

Compatibility

The first statement in this section, "peer editing is compatible with my teaching style," had a mean

of 4.80, median of 5, and mode of 5, indicating strongly that the majority of instructors believe that peer review is consistent with their teaching style. Data also suggests positive indications for the second statement, "peer editing is a good way to review writing," with a mean of 4.78, a mode of 5, and a median of 5. Compatibility provides positive reinforcement for the use of peer editing in writing classrooms, and it is particularly encouraging from a curriculum development perspective to see that instructors believe peer editing suits their teaching style. This is further enhanced by comments of teachers who suggested if peer editing were included in the curriculum, they would be flexible enough to adopt it.

Complexity

The first statement, "peer editing is easy to implement," had a mean, mode, median, and standard deviation of 3.39, 5.00, 4.00, and 1.50, respectively.

Brett Morgan has lived and taught in Japan and other Asian countries for over 20 years. He presently works as a full-time lecturer in the CISE at Ritsumeikan University, Japan.

This shows that teachers believe peer editing is somewhat easy to implement in their classroom. The second statement, "students need to be trained before they can implement peer editing," had a mean of 5.27, a mode and median of 6.00, and a standard deviation of 1.0. This strongly indicates that teachers believe that before conducting peer editing, students need to be trained on how to do it effectively, emphasizing the need for effective training programs to be implemented within EFL writing curricula. Comments from teachers further indicate that training is essential when conducting peer editing, especially for first-year students.

Demonstrability

The first statement, "peer editing increases the quality of students' final papers," had a mean and mode of 4.39, and a median of 5.00, indicating somewhat positive beliefs in the actual results of peer editing. The second statement, "peer editing helps students understand academic writing better," also proved somewhat positive, with a mean and mode of 4.71, and median of 5.00. These results analyzed together provide positive indications towards the visible results of peer editing. Comments from

teachers further suggest that within peer editing, layout is the easiest aspect for students to check, with reviewing for cohesion and comprehension considered more difficult to implement.

Use of Peer Editing

The first part of the qualitative section contained questions relating to the instructors' use of peer editing in their English classes. Participants answering "yes" were then asked to describe how they used peer editing, and those answering "no" to explain why they did not. Results clearly indicate that peer editing is widely used in their classrooms, with 70.7% of those surveyed using peer editing. For foreign instructors the percentage is 88.5%, and for Japanese instructors, 40%, clearly demonstrating that foreign instructors are using peer editing more.

Responses from foreign and Japanese instructors showed similar patterns in how they used peer editing. Comments indicate that most conduct peer editing work on a one-to-one basis; however, some also used small group reviews or a combination of both. This highlights that instructors find this process more complementary with pair work, and that they perceive one individual reviewing a students' work in detail as more beneficial than a small group working on several papers simultaneously. There were no comments explaining why teachers chose either process, an element worth examining in proceeding research. Most instructors conduct peer editing in the classroom, with comments suggesting the use of a structured peer review system. This entails either specifically teaching what is required to conduct peer editing, or providing a checklist of common writing mistakes and errors to look for. Only one instructor used a peer review checklist provided to them in the curriculum, which suggests that many have developed their own peer editing material to conduct these activities. Those using peer editing outside of class did so either by having students check each other's work via Google documents, or by having students take their peer's work home. These instructors did not indicate why they did not conduct peer review in class. Furthermore, two instructors who conduct peer review did not provide any comments.

Comments from Japanese and foreign instructors who do not use peer editing suggest that the reason is not necessarily due to a dislike for the process, but rather that their classes do not focus on writing

or contain simple writing activities which do not require peer editing.

Benefits of Peer Editing

The second open-ended question asked whether teachers felt there were any benefits in using peer editing. Most foreign instructors (92.4%) surveyed and 46.7% of Japanese believed there were definite benefits. Many comments indicated that the collaborative nature of peer reviews exposed students to other writing styles, which if more advanced than their own could prove beneficial. Some teachers suggested all levels of students could become consciously aware of their own mistakes through reviewing others' writing, providing opportunities to correct their own writing before submitting assignments for grades. Some also suggested that peer editing was essential for Japanese students as culturally they are used to working alone, and exposure to a collaborative style of learning helped prepare them for future work environments. Of the teachers that do not currently conduct peer review, the answers to this question were nonetheless positive. Both foreign and Japanese instructors could see potential benefits in peer editing, which suggests these teachers might employ peer editing in their classes if given the opportunity. Unfortunately, 24.4% of all participants, including 50% of Japanese instructors, did not write any comments. Another significant theme to emerge from the comments of several foreign and Japanese instructors was that while most believe conducting peer editing

Bjorn Fuisting is a full-time lecturer at Ritsumeikan University, Japan. He has been teaching in Japan for 10 years. His research interests include peer review, extensive reading and speed-reading.

Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Jeremy White at jwhite@rc.ritsumei.ac.jp

was beneficial, the time it took to train students how to peer edit effectively, the level of the students, or the seriousness of the students meant that peer editing was not a worthwhile task in their current environment, and that this class time would be better spent on actual writing itself.

Other Forms of Peer Review

The third open-ended question asked instructors to describe any other forms of peer review they use in their classroom. A majority (46.3%) of all instructors

use other forms of peer review. It is clear that foreign instructors do so more, 53.8%, compared to 33.3% of Japanese. The most common alternative use of peer review was in presentations, with students providing both formative and summative feedback on their peers' presentations. Few instructors provided detailed answers for not trying other forms of peer review, but some suggested that effective peer review was too time consuming, or that the feedback provided was of poor quality, and thus not worth using class time for.

Peer Evaluation

The final survey question asked instructors to describe their use of any form of peer evaluation that counted towards students' grades. A majority (56.1%) of all instructors, 65.4% of foreign instructors, and 40% of Japanese, indicated that they used peer evaluation. In most instances this was used for student presentations rather than writing activities, with many using peer evaluation informally to keep students engaged during presentations, or to provide alternative sources of feedback. This suggests that teachers are not overly confident in students' ability to give grades to other students. This was enhanced by the comments of those who do not use peer evaluation, with some stating they do not trust the opinions of students or that it would only work with small classes of high-level students.

Conclusion

Reflecting what has been found in the research on students' attitudes toward peer review in Japan and other EFL contexts, English instructors at this university clearly find value in peer review activities. Quantitative analysis indicates support for curricular adoption of peer review, showing that instructors are slightly positive to the relative advantage of peer review, fairly positive towards its results demonstrability, and strongly positive towards its compatibility, but also recognize peer review's complexity. Most foreign instructors and some Japanese use peer review in their classes, mostly for writing activities, but also for student presentations, and roughly half of participants use some form of peer evaluation. Many instructors, even if they do not use it, see benefits in peer review, especially in its interactive potential, but recognize challenges in its implementation. For those designing writing curricula, the implications of this study are that there

is obviously a desire from both Japanese and foreign teachers to have some form of peer review process, but unless it is specifically written into the curriculum with guided training for both teachers and students, it is unlikely to be universally implemented.

Limitations and Suggestions for Further Research

The findings of this study could be applicable to other Japanese university settings, and could also have relevance for other EFL learning environments. Possible limitations that must be considered in any interpretation, however, are the differing sample size of 26 foreign instructors and 15 Japanese, and the fact that 60% of English instructors at the university did not return the survey. It is possible that some did not complete the survey because they did not use peer review, which could impact the findings concerning peer review experience. Additionally, this study focused primarily on teachers' reported attitudes towards peer review, and the subject could benefit from a more in-depth qualitative approach to data collection, such as interviews, to discover more about both Japanese and foreign instructors' ideas for effective curricular implementation of peer review, something worth exploring in future research.

References

- Berg, C. (1999). The effects of trained peer response on ESL students' revision types and writing quality. *Journal of Second Language Writing*, 8(3), 215-241.
- Bruffee, K. A. (1984). Peer tutoring and the "conversation of mankind." In G. A. Olson (Ed.), *Writing centers: Theory and administration* (pp. 3-15). Urbana, IL: National Council of Teachers of English.
- Chang, C. F. (2012). Peer review via three modes in an EFL writing course. *Computers and Composition*, 29(1), 63-78.
- Chaudron, C. (1984). Evaluating writing: Effects of feedback on revision. *RELC Journal*, 15(2), 1-14.
- Coomber, M., & Silver, R. (2010). The effect of anonymity in peer review. In A. M. Stoke (Ed.), *JALT2009 Conference Proceedings* (pp. 621-631). Tokyo: JALT.
- Hayes, J. R., & Flower, L. (1980). Identifying the organization of writing processes. In L. W. Gregg & E. R. Steinber (Eds.), *Cognitive processes in writing* (pp. 3-29). Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum.

- Hirose, K. (2008). Peer feedback in L2 English writing instruction. In K. Bradford Watts, T. Muller, & M. Swanson (Eds.), *JALT2007 Conference Proceedings* (pp. 543-552). Tokyo: JALT.
- Hirvela, A. (1999). Collaborative writing instruction and communities of readers and writers. *TESOL Journal*, 8(2), 7-12.
- Hosack, I. (2003). The effects of anonymous feedback on Japanese university students' attitudes towards peer review. *Ritsumeikanhougaku bessatsu*, 1, 297-322.
- Jacobs, G., Curtis, A., Braine, G., & Huang, S. (1998). Feedback on student writing: Taking the middle path. *Journal of Second Language Writing*, 7(3), 307-317.
- Leki, I. (1990). Potential problems with peer responding in ESL writing classes. *CATESOL Journal*, 3(1), 5-19.
- Lockhart, C., & Ng, P. (1995). Analyzing talk in ESL peer response groups: Stances, functions, and content. *Language Learning*, 45(4), 605-651.
- Min, H. T. (2005). Training students to become successful peer reviewers. *System*, 33(2), 293-308.
- Moore, G. C., & Benbasat, I. (1991). Development of an instrument to measure the perceptions of adopting an information technology innovation. *Information Systems Research* 2(3), 192-222.
- Morgan, B., Fusting, B., & White, J., (2014). *Student attitudes towards peer review in EFL writing*. Manuscript submitted for publication.
- Morra, A. M., & Romano, M. E. (2008). University students' reactions to guided peer feedback of EAP compositions. *Journal of College Literacy & Learning*, 35, 19-30.
- Moussaoui, S. (2012). An investigation of the effects of peer evaluation in enhancing Algerian students' writing autonomy and positive affect. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 69, 1775-1784.
- Nelson, G. L., & Carson, J. G. (1998). ESL students' perceptions of effectiveness in peer response groups. *Journal of Second Language Writing*, 7(2), 113-131.
- Nelson, G. L., & Murphy, G. M. (1992). An L2 writing group: Talk and social dimension. *Journal of Second Language Writing*, 1, 171-193.
- Paulus, T. (1999). The effect of peer and teacher feedback on student writing. *Journal of Second Language Writing*, 8(3), 265-289.

- Rogers, E. M. (1983) *Diffusion of innovation* (3rd ed.). NY: The Free Press.
- Silver, R., & Coomber, M. (2011). How anonymity affects feedback in the peer review process. *KOTESOL Proceedings 2010* (pp. 299-308). Seoul: KOTESOL.
- Taferner, R. H. (2008). Toward effective EFL writing revision: Peer review. *OnCue Journal*, 2(2), 76-91.
- Taferner, R. H. (2009). Attitudes toward peer collaboration within the EFL writing context in Japan. In A. M. Stoke (Ed.), *JALT2008 Conference Proceedings* (pp. 1117-1125). Tokyo: JALT.
- Tsui, A. B. M., & Ng, M. (2000). Do secondary L2 writers benefit from peer comments? *Journal of Second Language Writing*, 9(2), 147-170.

- Vygotsky, L. (1978). *Mind in society*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Vygotsky, L. (1986). *Thought and language*. (A. Kozulin, Trans.). Cambridge, MA: Harvard MIT Press.
- Wakabayashi, R. (2008). The effect of peer feedback on EFL writing: Focusing on Japanese university students. *OnCue Journal*, 2(2), 92-110.
- Zacharias, N. T. (2007). Teacher and student attitudes toward teacher feedback. *RELC Journal*, 38(1), 38-52.
- Zhang, S. (1995). Reexamining the affective advantage of peer feedback in the ESL writing class. *Journal of Second Language Writing*, 4, 209-222.

Call for TESOL Arabia Conference Proceedings

The editors of the Proceedings of the 2014 TESOL Arabia Conference would like to invite you to submit a paper based on your presentation at the TESOL Arabia 2014 Conference to be considered for publication in the next volume of the Proceedings. Only those who presented at the Conference may submit articles for the Proceedings.

Please send your article to Publications Coordinator, Peter McLaren at: pmclaren@uaeu.ac.ae

The deadline for submissions is **October 1, 2014**.

Please follow the specifications outlined below:

- Articles should be 3000-4000 words.
- Articles should be typed using Times New Roman, font size 12, with 1½ line spacing.
- If you include tables and/or figures, make sure they are no wider than 12 cm.
- Do not use color in tables or figures.
- Do not use footnotes.
- Only use portrait orientation (i.e., do not insert any pages in landscape orientation).
- Remove all hyperlinks in the text.
- Include a complete list of references using APA style. Consult the Publications Manual of the American Psychological Association, 6th Edition (2009) if necessary.
- Send articles electronically as a Word attachment.

We will acknowledge receipt of articles within two weeks.